

BRAIN DOMINANCE AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF WOMEN COLLEGE STUDENTS IN TIRUNELVELI

M. Avoodaiammal @ Abirami* & Dr. Ramesh**

* Assistant Professor, EMG Yadava Women's College, Madurai, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor & Head Incharge, DDE, Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, Tirunelveli, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: M. Avoodaiammal @ Abirami & Dr. Ramesh, "Brain Dominance and Emotional Intelligence of Women College Students in Tirunelveli", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 2, Issue 1, Page Number 122-123, 2017.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2017 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Wisdom Know what is to do Next, Skill Knows How to do it, and Virtue is doing it:

The greatest discovery of this generation is that man can alter his life simply by altering his attitude of mind. Education is that process of development in which consists the passage of human being from infancy to maturity, the process whereby adapts himself gradually in various ways to his physical, social, spiritual environment. The function of education is conceived to be the adjustment of man to his environment to the end that the most enduring satisfaction may accrue to the individual and the society. Some educationists have defined only one aspect of education whereas the others emphasize its other phases.

Anatomy of Brain:

The brain as a central computer that controls all bodily functions, then the nervous system is like a network that relays messages back and forth from the brain to different parts of the body. It does this via the spinal cord, which runs from the brain down through the back and contains threadlike nerves that branch out to every organ and body part. When a message comes into the brain from anywhere in the body, the brain then sends a message back telling the muscles in your hands to pull away. Luckily this neurological relay race takes a lot less time than it just took to read about it. Considering everything it does, the human brain is incredibly compact, weighting just 3 pounds, its many folds and grooves though provide it with the additional surface area necessary for storing all of the body's important information. The spinal cord on the other hand is a long bundle of nerve tissue about 18 inches long and $\frac{3}{4}$ inch thick. It extends from the lower part of the brain down through spine. They are both cushioned by layers of membranes' calls meninges as well as special fluid called cerebrospinal fluid. This fluid helps protect the nerve tissue, keep it healthy and remove waste products. The brain is made up of three sections-the forebrain, the midbrain and the hind brain. The forebrain is the largest and most complex part of the brain. It consists of the cerebrum-the area with all the folds and grooves typically seen in pictures of the brain as well as some other structures beneath it.

The Midbrain:

The mid brain located underneath the middle of the fore brain acts as a master coordination for all the messages going in and out of the brain to spinal cord.

The Hind Brain:

The hind brain sits underneath the back end of the cerebrum and its consists of the cerebellum Pons and medulla oblongata. The cerebellum also called the little brain because it looks like a small version of the cerebellum it is responsible for balance, movement and coordination the pons and the medulla oblongata along with the midbrain are often called the brain stem. The brain stems takes in sends out and coordinate all of the brain messages. It also controls many of the body automatic function like breathing, heart rate, blood pressure, swallowing, digestion and blinking.

Reflective Thinking:

There are four thinking languages or modalities 1.kinesthetic thought2.auditory thought 3. Visual thought 4. Verbal thought. A person who is right brain dominant engages himself in the intellectual activity and he shines in the field of science which is related with the invention of new objects. A brain dominant person mostly be a left hander gives more effort to the right side of brain. Usually these right brain dominant people used to prefer the study of medicine, physics biological science etc., and these people are innovative. They try to pictures the objects which are abstracted and form the concrete objects. Reality is imaginative for them. They keep listening and observe the facts and findings of new objects. They do not sort interest in the orderly picturisation. They find to sort interest from the discovery of finding facts ideas and theories. Lawful effects are observed by them.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the significant difference in the left, right and mid brain dominance of first degree women students with regard to arts, science, commerce and professionals.
- ✓ To find out the significant difference in the left, right and mid brain dominance of first degree women students with regard to Autonomous college verse non- Autonomous College.

T - Test for Left Brain Dominance:

S.No	Nature of College	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' value	Table Value	Remark
1.	Co Education	49.0	7.12	1.42	0.07	1.96	NSD
	Women	34.0	7.15	1.71			

T - Test for Right Brain Dominance:

S.No	Nature of College	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark
2.	Co Education	47.00	15.13	1.42	0.04	1.96	NSD
	Women	27.00	15.11	1.88			

Method Chosen for the Study:

The method selected for this study was normative survey method. The investigator adopted survey method because of its following characteristics.

- ✓ It gathers data from a relatively large number of cases.
- ✓ It is concerned not with characteristics of individuals but with generalized statistics of whole population.
- ✓ It deals with clearly defined problems and has definite objectives. It requires an imaginative planning a careful analysis and interpretation of the data and a logical and skillful reporting of things.

Tools Used:

Questionnaire:

Statistical Technique Used:

In the data analysis, items were separately analyzed that is, they are grouped and analyzed. The collected data were synthesized and t test and anova were adopted to be bringing out results in the form of findings.

Findings:

- ✓ There is not any significant difference in the optional subject of the women students with regard to left brain dominance (Fratio is 0.42)
- ✓ There is not any significant difference in the optional subject of the women students with regard to right brain dominance (Fratio is 0.93)
- ✓ There is not any significance among women students studying in Women College and Co Education College with regard to left brain dominance.
- ✓ There is not any significance among women students studying in Women College and Co Education College with regard to right brain dominance.

Conclusion:

Brain dominance does depend upon the circumstances in which a person study. It depends on physical health and mind maturity.

References:

1. <https://www.psychologytoday.com/blog/the-brain-and-emotional-intelligence>
2. <http://www.danielgoleman.info/the-brain-and-emotional-intelligence-an-interview-with-daniel-goleman/>
3. <http://morethansound.net/shop/the-brain-and-emotional-intelligence-new-insight/>
4. C. Kothari, Research Methodology.